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Fez: Embracing sustainable tourism through tradition and innovation

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Abstract

In a world where sustainable development is becoming an undeniable priority, the tourism sector of Fez finds itself at a crossroads between the preservation of its immemorial cultural heritage and the adoption of innovative and sustainable practices. The city of Fez, with its medina listed as a UNESCO World Heritage Site, its traditional tanneries, and its rich architectural heritage, represents a living model of the fragile balance between tradition and modernity. This work proposes to explore the strategies and initiatives put in place in Fez to promote sustainable tourism which respects and enhances its unique heritage while responding to contemporary environmental and societal challenges.

We will first analyze how Fez manages the influx of visitors while respecting its urban and natural environment, highlighting the challenges and successes of this integration. Next, we will examine the technological and organizational innovations adopted by tourism stakeholders in Fez, such as waste management, water conservation, renewable energy, and digital services for tourists, which contribute to a development more sustainable city. Finally, we will discuss the importance of community engagement and participatory governance in creating an enriching tourism experience that benefits both visitors and local people.

The objective of this communication is to highlight good practices and lessons learned from Fez in terms of sustainable tourism, thus offering avenues for reflection and action for other heritage destinations around the world. By recognizing the value of tradition while embracing innovation, Fez is positioning itself as a leader in the transformation towards more sustainable and responsible tourism.

Keywords: Tourism; Sustainable tourism; Innovation; Fez; Historic city.

1. Introduction

Historically, tourism evolved into a global activity during the 20th century, positioning itself as the world's leading economic activity. This sector is now a key economic pillar for many countries, whether developed or developing, where it is considered a crucial driver of their growth.

Tourism is recognized for its important role in economic and social development. It contributes significantly to job creation, directly affecting the tourism sector and, indirectly, other sectors through economic spinoffs. Furthermore, travel and tourism stimulates investment in infrastructure and generates a significant amount of foreign exchange.

The tourism sector is also a large consumer of handicraft products, influencing rural and urban industries as well as suppliers of basic furniture and equipment. More than an economic activity, tourism facilitates cultural exchanges and dialogue between cultures, especially in destinations popular with mass tourism.

The transformations in tourist areas are profound and promote cultural openness, broadening the possibilities for dialogue between different cultures and strengthening international cooperation. The increase in tourist flows and the

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democratization of tourism are supported by economic factors such as increased purchasing power and greater availability of leisure time, consequences of post-World War II economic growth.

Growing urbanization and technological innovations, particularly in transportation, have also played a crucial role in the expansion of tourism. These developments have allowed wider access to tourism, going beyond traditional modes of transport such as the train, and favoring the use of automobiles and planes.

Recognition of the negative consequences of uncontrolled tourism growth has led to a more recent awareness. Previously dominated by a quantitative perspective, tourism management is evolving towards an approach more respectful of natural and cultural resources, promoting authentic and quality tourism.

The crisis of the traditional economic model of tourism has prompted the emergence of new demands for sustainable tourism, integrating principles of sustainable development. This involves tourism that meets current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs, in harmony with the preservation of the environment and local cultural identities.

In this context, sustainable development takes a prominent place in business strategies and government policies related to tourism, emphasizing environmental and social responsibility. These strategies aim to ensure the sustainability of the sector to ensure continued economic benefits for host communities.

The tourism sector identifies itself as a historic vector of economic growth throughout the world, as well as for Morocco, by playing a crucial role in the sustainable development and elevation of the socio-economic competitiveness of its tourist destinations. This is particularly the case for the city of Fez, renowned for its tourist offer with a strong cultural tone.

Fez, one of the oldest imperial cities in Morocco, perfectly illustrates the intersection between tradition and modernity, making it a favored destination for tourists from around the world. The city is most famous for its medieval medina, a UNESCO World Heritage Site, which is a vibrant labyrinth of historic markets, ancient mosques, and madrassas. This rich heritage not only contributes to the tourist attraction of the city but also reinforces its image as a cultural and spiritual center, vital for cultural tourism in Morocco. By integrating these traditional aspects with modern preservation and promotion initiatives, Fez continues to stand out as a model of sustainable tourism development.

Faced with the urgency of environmental challenges and the need for inclusive economic growth, this study aims to explore the dynamics of innovation in the tourism sector in Fez. By specifically questioning the role of new technologies and innovative practices in the promotion of sustainable tourism, the central problem of this research is the following: how can innovation initiatives in the tourism sector contribute to the transformation of Fez into a sustainable tourism destination?

2. Literature review

2.1. Evolution of tourism and its global impact

Tourism, often cited as one of the most influential and dynamic industries in the world, has undergone profound evolution during the 20th century. Initially perceived as a luxury reserved for the elite, it has now become a global activity, affecting millions of people around the world [1]. This democratization of tourism was driven by technological advances in transportation and communication, as well as a general increase in living standards, making travel accessible to a much wider segment of the population. This expansion has transformed tourism into a major pillar of global economies, capable of generating large-scale employment and driving economic development in regions that might otherwise remain marginalized.

The economic impact of tourism is undeniable, as evidenced by various studies that show how this industry stimulates local economic growth by creating jobs, increasing business revenues and providing financial resources for public infrastructure [2]. Tourism activities also encourage heritage conservation, cultural revitalization and improvement of local services, thereby contributing significantly to the social and economic development of nations.

However, the picture is not entirely positive. The rapid development of tourism has also raised significant concerns related to its environmental and socio-cultural impact [3]. Popular destinations often suffer from overtourism, which can lead to degradation of the natural environment, dilution of cultural authenticity, and deterioration in the quality of life of local residents. Congestion, pollution, loss of biodiversity, and wear and tear of historic and natural sites are some

of the environmental problems exacerbated by unregulated tourism. Socioculturally, although tourism can foster an enriching cultural exchange, it can also lead to commercialization of culture, creating situations where traditions are modified or exaggerated to satisfy tourist expectations.

As a result, many researchers and practitioners are calling for a reassessment of tourism practices to move towards a more sustainable model. This sustainable tourism model not only seeks to minimize negative impacts on the environment and local communities, but also aims to create a lasting positive economic impact. The adoption of sustainable management practices, raising tourists' awareness of the impact of their travels, and engaging local communities in tourism development are key strategies to achieve this objective. Sustainability in tourism is no longer just an option, but a necessity to preserve natural and cultural resources for future generations while enjoying their immediate economic benefits.

2.2. Mass tourism and its challenges

The phenomenon of mass tourism has transformed many destinations around the world, characterized mainly by a considerable increase in visitor flows. This growth, while economically beneficial, has often led to undesirable side effects on the destinations themselves. According to a report by the World Tourism Organization [4], the massive influx of tourists to popular places has frequently resulted in their overcrowding. This overload has placed immense pressure on local infrastructure, accelerating the wear and tear of heritage sites and worsening environmental impacts such as pollution and degradation of natural habitats.

Moreover, as Cohen noted in 1972 [5], the rise of mass tourism has often led to a homogenization of tourist experiences. In an effort to satisfy high volumes of tourists, many sites have adapted their offerings to meet stereotypical expectations, resulting in a standardization that erodes the cultural authenticity of destinations. This standardization often extends beyond tourist attractions to include gastronomy, souvenirs, and even cultural performances, transforming unique cultural practices into commodified products for tourist consumption.

The erosion of cultural heritage mentioned by Cohen also reveals a significant reduction in the quality of interactions between visitors and local communities. Rather than deep and meaningful cultural exchanges, interactions can become superficial, limited to commercial transactions where local residents are seen as parts of a picturesque backdrop for tourists' photos. This dynamic not only alters the experience of visitors, who fail to gain a true insight into local culture, but also disrupts the lifestyles of host communities. Residents may find themselves marginalized in their own homes, with traditions and lifestyles altered to meet the expectations of tourists.

2.3. Transition to sustainable tourism

In response to the challenges posed by mass tourism, the concept of sustainable tourism emerged, inspired by the principles of sustainable development formulated at the Earth Summit in Rio in 1992 [6]. Sustainable tourism aims to minimize the negative impacts of tourism while maximizing its economic, social and environmental benefits for destinations [7]. Sustainable tourism initiatives in Fez, for example, have integrated practices that respect and value cultural heritage while promoting community engagement and environmental preservation.

2.4. Sustainable tourism in historic cities

Historic cities like Fez and Kyoto recognize the crucial importance of sustainable tourism for their long-term preservation. These cities, rich in historical and cultural heritage, face unique challenges linked to the management of tourist flows and the protection of their cultural and environmental treasures. In Kyoto, for example, the response to these challenges has been the implementation of sustainable tourism policies that aim to reduce negative impacts on heritage while maximizing positive benefits for the local community. According to Okazaki [8], these measures include initiatives to regulate the number of visitors to sensitive sites, promote environmentally friendly activities, and encourage the involvement of local residents in tourism development and management.

In Fez, similar to Kyoto, cultural heritage serves as both a foundation and a lever for tourism. However, the city has also adopted a proactive approach to safeguarding this heritage by integrating sustainable tourism practices. This includes restoration projects that use traditional techniques and materials to preserve architectural integrity while meeting modern standards for sustainability. Additionally, Fez promotes tourism experiences that enrich visitors' understanding and appreciation of local culture, such as educational tours and craft workshops that highlight the skills and traditions of local artisans.

2.5. Sustainable development models

Heritage cities, faced with the need to protect their cultural and environmental integrity while welcoming visitors, have explored and adopted various sustainable development models to manage the tourist influx responsibly. A particularly relevant model is that of “carrying capacity”, which aims to determine the maximum visitors that a site can accommodate without suffering unacceptable negative effects. McCool and Lime [9] emphasize that this concept is crucial for preserving the quality of the tourist experience while minimizing impacts on heritage and the natural environment.

Venice, for example, is a city that has been forced to implement carrying capacity management strategies due to its extreme popularity with tourists. The city experiences enormous pressure during peak attendance, which has direct consequences on its infrastructure, its environment and its local population. Measures adopted include regulating visitor flows in the most sensitive areas, using technology to track and control the number of people present at any given time, and even introducing entry tickets during periods high influx to reduce pressure on the city.

These carrying capacity-based approaches are not just limited to limiting numbers. They also include educational initiatives aimed at raising tourists' awareness of the importance of heritage preservation. By informing visitors of the issues and impacts of their presence, we encourage more respectful behavior, which contributes to a sustainable and enriching tourist experience for all.

Application of the carrying capacity model requires a thorough understanding of available resources, local community needs and visitor expectations. This often involves close collaboration between local authorities, tourism management organizations, tourism businesses and residents, to find a balance that respects the capacity of the environment while providing a positive experience for tourists.

2.6. Specific sustainability practices

Sustainability certification initiatives for tourism businesses have become crucial tools in promoting eco-responsible practices within the tourism industry. These programs provide guidelines and criteria that businesses can follow to minimize their environmental impact while maximizing social and economic benefits for local communities. A prominent example of such initiatives is that of the Global Sustainable Tourism Council (GSTC), which plays a significant role in establishing universal standards for sustainability in tourism.

The GSTC develops and manages global criteria, known as the GSTC Criteria, which serve as an international benchmark for sustainability in travel and tourism. The GSTC Criteria are divided into four main pillars: sustainable management, socio-economic impacts, cultural conservation, and environmentalism. These criteria not only help businesses to operate sustainably, but also destinations to plan, develop and manage tourism activity responsibly [10].

Certifications based on GSTC criteria are sought by tourism businesses wanting to demonstrate their commitment to sustainable development. By obtaining these certifications, companies can not only improve their reputation and competitiveness in the market, but also attract customers who are increasingly aware of the importance of environmental and social issues. These certifications often require companies to undergo regular audits and show continuous improvements in their practices.

Additionally, GSTC collaborates with national and regional bodies to adapt its criteria to different cultural and environmental contexts, ensuring that sustainable practices are relevant and effective regardless of location. This allows for wider implementation of sustainable practices and encourages a more holistic approach to sustainable tourism development.

2.7. Contextualization of sustainable tourism in Fez

Fez, often described as the spiritual and cultural capital of Morocco, presents a unique example of a historic city that has embraced sustainable tourism while preserving its rich cultural heritage. The city, famous for its UNESCO World Heritage medina [11], has embarked on a series of initiatives aimed at integrating the principles of sustainable development into its tourism practices. These efforts are not only motivated by the need to preserve its centuries-old architecture and traditions, but also by the desire to respond to contemporary economic and social challenges.

2.7.1. Integration of sustainable practices

Tourism in Fez has historically been a significant economic driver, but the growing influx of visitors has posed sustainability challenges. To respond to this, the city has implemented policies and projects that promote a balanced

approach to tourism. For example, restorations and renovations of the medina have been undertaken using techniques and materials that respect historical and environmental integrity. Initiatives such as limiting motorized traffic in the old town help preserve the unique atmosphere of the medina while reducing pollution.

2.7.2. Promotion of eco-tourism

At the same time, Fez has encouraged the development of eco-tourism by supporting eco-friendly accommodation and guided tours that educate visitors about local history and the importance of conservation. These tours often highlight artisan workshops, providing a first-hand view of the traditional manufacturing of Fez products, such as ceramics and leatherwork, which are made using traditional and sustainable methods.

Since the creation of the Moroccan Charter for Responsible Tourism[15] and the Morocco Sustainable Tourism Trophies, Morocco is committed to ensuring that its tourism is particularly respectful of the environment through numerous standards. Each year, more and more establishments or places in the country are recognized for their environmental responsibility.

2.7.3. Some tourism figures in Fez:

Some 219,047 overnight stays were recorded during the first three months of 2023, compared to 102,631 overnight stays during the same period of 2022, indicate data from the National Tourism Observatory [12].

2.7.4. Community engagement

Community engagement in Fez in the area of sustainable tourism is also notable. Local residents are often involved in the planning and execution of tourism initiatives, ensuring that tourism benefits return to the community. For example, community-based tourism projects have been established so that tourism benefits directly support education and infrastructural development.

2.7.5. Challenges and perspectives

Despite these efforts, Fez faces constant challenges, including the need to manage the balance between increasing tourism and preserving its living environment. The city continues to seek innovative strategies to improve the sustainability of its tourism sector without compromising its cultural and natural heritage.

2.8. Tourism: Fez, fourth best cultural destination in the world

Morocco continues to strengthen its reputation as a preferred tourist destination, as shown by the recent ranking of Tripadvisor[16], the world's largest travel advice platform. In January 2024, Fez, the spiritual capital of Morocco, was ranked among the top ten global cultural destinations, occupying fourth position just behind Cuba, Cusco (Peru) and Agra (India). The imperial city thus surpasses renowned cities such as Athens, Dublin, Edinburgh and Tokyo in this ranking.

According to Tripadvisor, cultural travel remains popular with a quarter (25%) of Americans surveyed saying they are planning cultural tourism trips in the coming months.

2.9. Fez and its vulnerabilities

The urban districts of Fez[17] are experiencing notable demographic, geographic and economic expansion. The local economy relies heavily on tourism and an efficient transportation network that facilitates the movement of people and goods both internationally and to other major Moroccan cities located on the coast.

However, Fez faces several natural hazards such as fires, earthquakes, floods, heat waves and storms. The growing impact of climate change is putting increasing pressure on the region's environment, affecting people and their livelihoods. Vulnerability to natural disasters varies from one neighborhood to another, depending on the capacity of communities, infrastructure and services to adapt. Some vulnerabilities are specific to specific sites, while others, more systemic, require an integrated approach to build resilience to potential risks.

3. Material and methods

As part of this research dedicated to sustainable tourism in Fez, we conducted a qualitative survey with 11 owners of riads, the best rated by visitors on Booking [13], located in the medina of Fez. These semi-structured interviews, carried

out in 2024, made it possible to explore the owners' perceptions of sustainable tourism practices and the innovations implemented in their establishments. Our semi-structured interview guide included open-ended questions that revolved around sustainability and innovation issues in the specific context of Fez. Data collection was stopped after 11 interviews because responses began to repeat themselves, indicating that we had reached a point of data saturation where no significant new information was being added.

The choice of semi-structured interviews was guided by the desire to combine structure and flexibility, thus making it possible to deepen the responses while following a pre-established outline which ensures the coherence of the data collected. This method is particularly suited to social science research where individual perceptions and experiences are at the heart of the analysis. The questions were designed to encourage open but focused discussion, thereby facilitating the emergence of rich and detailed data, while remaining aligned with the specific objectives of our study.

Data analysis was conducted manually, which involved extensive and repeated reading of the transcripts to develop an intimate and nuanced understanding of the responses provided. This manual process of thematic coding allowed us to detect themes and patterns directly from the data, avoiding the constraints sometimes imposed by qualitative analysis software. This methodological choice reinforced our commitment to an authentic and personalized interpretation of participants' perspectives, which is crucial for a study that focuses on the complex dynamics of sustainable tourism in a setting as unique as the medina of Fez.

The main objective of this study was to analyze how these owners integrate sustainable tourism practices into the daily management of their riads and to understand the factors that contribute to the success and sustainability of these practices in a historic urban environment. Before beginning each interview, we took care to present the objectives of our study, as well as to emphasize the importance of confidentiality and anonymity of the responses collected. The questions in the interview guide were organized according to five or four themes, presented as follows:

1: General Information

- Context of the establishment
- History and development
- Reception capacity and staff

2: Sustainable Tourism Practices

- Environmental practices
- Community engagement

3: Innovation and Tradition

- Integration of tradition into innovation
- Customer perception

4: Challenges and Opportunities

- Obstacles
- Future vision

4. Results

As part of this research, interviews were conducted with managers of different Riads located in the heart of the medina of Fez, a city renowned for its rich cultural and historical heritage. These interviews aimed to capture current practices in sustainable tourism, innovation while preserving tradition, as well as the community commitment of these establishments typical of Moroccan accommodation. The methodology adopted for this data collection consisted of a structured interview guide to explore various aspects of Riad management. The results obtained offer a valuable perspective on how these traditional establishments adapt to the contemporary demands of eco-tourism while promoting their cultural heritage. This synthetic analysis of the responses aims to highlight the main trends and challenges encountered by Riads in the context of sustainable tourism in Fez.

4.1. General Information and History of the Riads

The responses indicate a rich variety in history and development of Riads in Fez, ranging from the 16th to the 20th century. Each Riad has been restored to combine architectural authenticity with modern amenities for the comfort of guests. Capacity varies, with teams of staff adapted to provide a personalized and specialized service, particularly in traditional Moroccan cuisine.

4.1.1. Sustainable Tourism Practices

Environmental Management

The majority of Riads have adopted eco-responsible practices such as the recycling of gray water, the use of solar panels and local and ecological building materials.

Community Engagement

It is clear that the inclusion of the local community is a strong pillar, with jobs mainly filled by local residents and partnerships with artisans for workshops. The Riads also support educational initiatives and sustainable development projects.

4.2. Innovation and Tradition

A reconciliation between tradition and innovation is observed, where Riads preserve traditional elements while integrating modern technologies to improve efficiency and comfort. This includes eco-friendly heating and cooling systems, smart installations for energy management, and the use of digital technologies for booking and managing services.

4.3. Customer Perception

Guests highly value the Riads' commitment to sustainability and cultural authenticity. They particularly appreciate the harmony between modern comfort and respect for traditions, as well as initiatives that allow direct interaction with local culture.

4.4. Challenges and Opportunities

Key challenges include maintaining the structural and aesthetic integrity of old buildings while integrating modern technologies. The Riads plan to increase their energy autonomy and continue to innovate in sustainable tourism practices to meet a growing demand for responsible and enriching travel experiences.

5. Discussion

During the qualitative interviews conducted with the 11 owners of the highest rated riads on BOOKING, we first explored the various aspects and dimensions of sustainable management practices and strategies adopted to ensure the growth and survival of their establishments, such as that are discussed in the literature.

5.1. General Information and History of the Riads

The historical richness of Riads in Fez is a major attraction for visitors seeking an authentic immersion in Moroccan heritage. The restoration of the Riads, which combines architectural authenticity and modern comfort, illustrates an adaptive strategy to meet the expectations of contemporary tourists while preserving the cultural essence of the structures. The variability of reception capacity and the specialization of staff in traditional cuisine reinforce this aspect, offering a personalized experience that enhances the local culinary heritage.

5.2. Sustainable Tourism Practices

5.2.1. Environmental Management:

Adopting eco-friendly practices such as recycling gray water and using solar panels shows awareness and commitment to environmental sustainability. These practices are not only beneficial to the environment but also serve as examples of sustainable practices in the tourism sector.

5.2.2. Community Engagement:

Hiring local residents and collaborating with artisans demonstrates successful socio-economic integration that contributes to local economic vitality. These initiatives promote inclusive tourism and support the preservation of traditional know-how.

5.3. Innovation and Tradition

The duality between preservation of traditions and integration of technological innovations in the Riads is a delicate balance that has been well maintained. By preserving traditional elements while integrating modern technologies, the Riads offer a rich and contemporary experience without sacrificing their cultural identity. This demonstrates a thoughtful fusion of past and present, essential for survival and relevance in an ever-changing tourism market.

5.4. Customer Perception

High customer satisfaction with the Riads' commitment to sustainability and authenticity highlights the importance of these values in choosing tourist accommodation. Appreciation for the harmony between modern comfort and respect for traditions indicates a growing demand for travel experiences that are both comfortable and culturally enriching.

5.5. Challenges and Opportunities

The challenges of maintaining the integrity of historic buildings while integrating modern technologies are significant but manageable with innovative and heritage-friendly approaches. Increasing energy autonomy and continuing innovation in sustainable tourism practices are key strategies to meet growing demand for more responsible tourism. This represents an opportunity for Riads to become leaders in the field of sustainable tourism.

In short, the results of this study highlight the way in which Riads in Fez have been able to evolve and adapt to meet the needs of a tourist market seeking authenticity and respect for the environment. Their ability to integrate sustainability into their operations while preserving and promoting their cultural heritage is an inspiring model for global sustainable tourism.

6. Conclusion

The in-depth study of sustainable tourism in Fez, a Moroccan city rich in tradition and innovation, reveals a fruitful convergence between the preservation of cultural heritage and the adoption of modern sustainable practices. By integrating ecological strategies such as waste management, water conservation and renewable energy, Fez is not only positioning itself as an environmentally conscious city, but also as a model for global sustainable tourism. This research highlights how innovative and environmentally friendly solutions can coexist with deep respect for cultural traditions, providing an enriching and responsible tourism experience.

The results of this study highlight the importance of community engagement and participatory governance in tourism development. By actively involving the local community in tourism initiatives, Fez promotes development that benefits both residents and visitors, thereby strengthening the socio-economic benefits of tourism while minimizing its environmental impacts.

Faced with the challenges of mass tourism, which can compromise local quality of life and environmental integrity, Fez has demonstrated an ability to balance tourism growth and sustainability. The practices put in place to regulate visitor flows and promote behaviors respectful of heritage illustrate a proactive and thoughtful strategy to ensure the long-term viability of its tourism and cultural resources.

Moving forward, it is crucial that Fez continues to develop policies that support innovation while respecting its traditions. The continued adoption of clean technologies and the promotion of tourism based on knowledge and respect for cultural and natural heritage will be essential to maintain the city's position as a leader in sustainable tourism in Morocco. In addition, increased collaboration between tourism stakeholders, local authorities and the international community could promote the sharing of best practices and strengthen the resilience of Fez in the face of global economic and environmental challenges.

In conclusion, Fez does not just meet the current requirements of sustainable tourism, it redefines them. By cleverly blending tradition and innovation, Fez not only inspires other cultural destinations, but also forges a path to a future where tourism supports sustainable growth while enriching the human experience.

6.1. Theoretical Implications

This research contributes to the literature on sustainable tourism by illustrating how a historic city can integrate sustainable practices while promoting its cultural heritage. Theoretically, it strengthens sustainable tourism models which advocate a holistic approach integrating environment, economy and social aspects. It highlights the complex dynamics between conservation and development, providing a frame of reference for further studies on the sustainable management of World Heritage sites. Additionally, this study extends the understanding of the role of local communities in co-creating the tourism experience, supporting theories that emphasize the importance of stakeholder [14] engagement in sustainable tourism success.

6.2. Practical Implications

On a practical level, the findings of this research offer valuable guidelines for urban planners and policy makers in heritage cities. First, the importance of participatory governance and community engagement must be emphasized in tourism policies, ensuring that the benefits of tourism are equitably distributed and that local residents are stakeholders in this industry. Second, the study suggests concrete methods to integrate sustainable technologies into tourism infrastructure without compromising the cultural integrity of the sites. This includes the adoption of renewable energy sources, efficient waste management and the use of eco-friendly building materials during restorations.

Furthermore, this study encourages historic cities to develop strategies to manage tourist flows, thereby minimizing the negative impacts of overtourism. Adopting digital technologies for controlling tourist flows and implementing tiered pricing policies can be effective solutions to balance access and conservation. Ultimately, it is essential to continue to promote tourism experiences that educate visitors about the importance of sustainability, thereby strengthening their environmental and cultural awareness.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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